

IASLIC

Bulletin

**A Peer-reviewed
Quarterly Journal**

Vol. 66 No. 4 December 2021

**CODEN IASLA 9
ISSN 0018-8441**

- **Eleven Habits of Successful Librarians**
- **Comparison of Publication Trends of two LIS Journals**
- **Online YouTube Videos on Library Cataloguing**
- **Library Literacy Initiatives in State Universities**
- **Library Networking Services for Differently-abled Students**
- **Online Research Support Tools in University Libraries**

Indian Association of Special Libraries & Information Centres

Kolkata - 700054

IASLIC Bulletin

A Peer-Reviewed Quarterly Journal
of Indian Association of Special Libraries and Information Centres

CODEN IASLA 9 ♦ ISSN 0018-8441

VOL. 66 NO. 4, DECEMBER 2021

CONTENTS

Eleven Habits of Successful Librarians S G Mahajan	195
Publication Trends of IASLIC Bulletin and Journal of Indian Library Association during 2010-2019 : A Bibliometric Comparison Dhiman Mondal, Mintu Halder and Nitai Raychoudhury	204
Online YouTube Videos on Library Cataloguing : An Analysis of Concepts and Practices Kanchan Pal and Sharad Kumar Sonkar	215
Library Literacy Initiatives in State Universities in Karnataka, India Hemavathi B N and Ramesha	225
Library Networking Services for the Differently - abled Students in Kerala : A Proposal of State Consortium for Inclusive Libraries with Assistive Technologies (SCILAT) V S Midhula Soman and K G Sudhier	235
Online Research Support Tools in University Libraries : An Exploratory Study Aditi Das and Swapna Banerjee	247

© IASLIC

No part of this publication may be reproduced in any material form including photocopying or storing it in any medium by electronic means and whether or not transiently or incidentally to some other use of this publication without the written permission of the copyright owner except in accordance with the provisions of the Copyright Act. Author's final version can be used for self-archiving with acknowledgement, attribution and credit for its published work in this journal.

Library Networking Services for the Differently-abled Students in Kerala: A Proposal of State Consortium for Inclusive Libraries with Assistive Technologies (SCILAT)

V S Midhula Soman^a and K G Sudhier^b

Abstract

Purpose : This paper aims to propose a state library consortium of learning resource centres (LRC) with Assistive Technologies (AT), which needs to be tied up with the services of the national institutes, to provide services to the differently-abled students in Kerala.

Design : The authors attempt to review the present status of differently-abled students and the libraries of the inclusive as well as the special schools in the state of Kerala, which function without any cooperation or networking. The paper describes a well-designed network for bringing all school libraries attached to the education department of the Government of Kerala, and other institutions of national importance in the state.

Findings : This paper highlights the need of a state level consortium for inclusive libraries with assistive technologies, its establishment, framework and mode of operation. The proposed three tier network comprises of the network of library systems of individual schools in the state, a state level network of the institutions identified for different types of disabilities maintained by a network control centre and specific national institutes (orthopedic, visual and hearing impaired) identified for the purpose. The study covers various aspects of the consortia such as the infrastructure, information services provided, software aspects etc. It also enumerates the salient features and significance of establishing such consortium.

Originality : Developing integrated and contemporary policies for the development of school library networks and consortia initiatives will help the special need children.

Keywords: Differently-abled student; Assistive technology; Learning resource centre; Inclusive education; Inclusive library; State consortium; Kerala.

1 Introduction

The information needs of differently-abled students have become complex and problematic due to inadequate information sources and services. Assistive technology (AT) plays a crucial role in the teaching-learning process of the differently-abled students. Effective use of ATs can also help governments and organisations to achieve inclusive education for the children

with disabilities in schools.

It is possible to provide user-friendly and adequate services for these people who have been neglected for a long. Availability of various e-resources have prompted libraries to transform its activities and services. The differently-abled students would access their required information in electronic format which would be converted into a medium that'll be accessible using assistive

^a Librarian, Sree Sankara College, Kalady, Ernakulam, Kerala -683574 ✉ vs.midhulasoman@gmail.com

^b Assistant Professor, Dept of Library & Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Neelakudi Campus, Kangalancherry, Post Thiruvavur, Tamil Nadu- 610 005, ☎ 9446484561 ✉ kgsudhier@cutn.ac.in

technologies. It creates a barrier free environment which helps them to access the required information independently. The term 'barrier free' indicates an environment where all users irrespective of their physical disadvantages can enter, use or access the resources as and when they require^[1].

There are quite a number of challenges for differently-abled students in accessing information in libraries. A visually challenged student cannot access the required information from a printed document or from other sources independently. A speech impaired student can not express his information needs to another person directly in a normal way. An orthopedically challenged student may not access a document independently which is kept in racks, or physical barriers may limit them to access an institution. Libraries, which are now tranforwd into Learning Resource Centres (LRCs), can equip themselves with the latest technologies to collect, store and disseminate information to the differently-abled in their preferred format. Thus libraries and information centres around the world are providing specialised services to the differently-abled users, in order to meet their information requirements. There are several national institutes for differently-abled students in India which caters information among such students. But the reach of these institutions are limited. Their services are confined to only their students. These situations need to change their attitude as these institutes failed to reach all such population in India. So this study aims to propose a school library consortium with assistive technologies, which needs to be tied up with the national institutes, to provide services to the differently-abled students in Kerala.

2 Inclusive Education

The Government of India is committed to provide education through mainstream schools

for children with disabilities as per the *Persons with Disability Act, 1995*^[2] and all the schools in the country are supposed to be disabled-friendly by 2020. Enrolment and retention of all children with disabilities in the mainstream education system should be ensured providing need based educational and other support to these children in order to develop their learning and abilities. The special interventions and strategies like pedagogic improvement and adoption of child centered practices are focused on the children with disabilities^[3]. Inclusive education (IE) is a new approach towards educating the children with disability and learning difficulties with that of normal ones within the same roof. It aims at integrated development of children with special needs and normal children through mainstream schooling^[4]. Consequent on the success of international experiments in placing children with disabilities in regular schools, the Planning Commission in 1971 included in its plan a programme for integrated education^[5]. The Government launched the Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC) scheme in December 1974. It was a centrally sponsored scheme aimed to provide educational opportunities to children with special needs in regular schools and to facilitate their achievement and retention. All the schools in the area are expected to enrol children with disabilities. In 1997 the philosophy of inclusive education is added in District Primary Education Programme (DPEP)^[6]. Many states had conducted surveys, assessment camps and evolved strategies to provide resource support to those children with special needs who were enrolled in DPEP schools. The thrust was on imparting quality education to all disabled children. To develop curriculum for special education and its inclusion in general teacher preparation programs, Rehabilitation Council of India (RCI)^[7] made a collaboration with National

Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) on 2005. Of late, a consensus has emerged among Indian intellectuals and pedagogues for adopting inclusive education in mainstream schools^[8]. The Government of India's National Education Policy (NEP-2020) also emphasised the need of inclusive education in its final recommendation^[9]. Figure 1 shows the different types of schools providing various types of education for the differently-abled children in India.

Figure 1: Types of Schools for the Disabled Children

3 Review of Literature

Many scholars have studied on the assistive technologies and LRCs for differently-abled students, and on consortia of library resource sharing networks. Nisbet^[10] presented data from a survey of qualified teachers of the visually impaired in respect of technologies and strategies used by 325 students with visual impairment and found that up to 16% of these learners are using screen reader tools in school. The article

concludes with recommendations for regulators and providers of assessments. Roy, Bandyopadhyay and Panigrahi^[11] carried out a study to find out the existing role of university and college libraries in West Bengal in facilitating their students with visual impairment by providing special required services. They identified the gap of special services requirement and services available.

Ravindran^[12] presented a proposal to bring the university and college libraries in Kerala under one network named Kerala Academic Libraries Network (KALNET). A network of the library systems of the individual universities in the state, with the respective university libraries as the apex, and a state level network of the individual university networks. Khowaja and Fatima^[13] in their study, determined the knowledge resources provided by the central university libraries to visually impaired people in India. The study identified information services provided by the universities and the difficulties encountered in providing services to visually impaired users. Mahawariya^[14] explored needs and requirements of visually impaired students and the facilities provided to them by the University of Delhi. The findings revealed that visually impaired students are provided with braille books, big screen computers with assistive technologies, recorded audio books in CDs or cassettes and other infrastructure facilities by their respective libraries.

Roy, Bandyopadhyay and Panigrahi^[15] studied the challenges faced by visually impaired students in the University of Calcutta. They found that the students are facing different difficulties in accessing relevant information. Bhardwaj^[16] highlighted that the facilities for visually impaired students in the libraries of higher educational institutions in Delhi. It was found that the facilities are insufficient for those

students to conduct study and research with existing technological infrastructure. Nandi, Panigrahi and Rath^[17] in their review depicted the revolution of the library cooperation to the academic library consortia for a period of 1998 to 2016. They found that the formation of the consortia is highly demanded for scholarly publications and subscribing e-resources; and the institutional repositories has become the new trend of academic library consortia. Desai, Mantha and Phalle^[18] in their paper concentrated on the possibilities of the assistive devices having minimal cost with advanced sensor technology, which will be effective for the Indian disabled population. In India, statistics disclosed that disabled people are more in rural areas than in urban areas and the reason behind this is the absence of best practices in assistive devices in rural area. Gupta^[19] discussed the importance of accessibility and need for universal design, and it is based on the premise that buildings, policies, technology and products must be designed in such a way that it is usable by all intended users and offers highest level of independence. Abdelrahman^[20] highlighted that library technologies and services were inadequate in the University of Khartoum, Sudan and they faced difficulties while accessing information. To overcome this barrier library must arrange for training of visually impaired students as well as staff for using assistive technologies satisfactorily.

Midhula Soman and Sudhier^[21] investigated the awareness and usage of internet resources among visually challenged students in Thiruvananthapuram district, Kerala. It was found that students are depending on internet resources mainly for their academic purpose. Kumar and Sanaman^[22] mentioned that assistive technologies such as audio web browsers, modified computer keyboards and screen readers or braille output can effectively provide access to

information to students with visual disability. Sharma and Das^[23] discussed various initiatives taken by the government since India's independence to provide education to school-aged children with disabilities. Authors made an attempt to identify the challenges that the country continues to face in providing education to this population and possible ways in which the challenges could be addressed. Haneefa and Syamili^[24] examined the use of ICT by the visually-impaired students in the Calicut University, Kerala. Findings revealed that most of the students are computer literates, and they use mobile phones frequently. Sreekumar and Vijayakumar^[25] visualised the conceptual framework and proposed the development of a Kerala Library Network (KELNET) by exploring and exploiting the available and the existing social infrastructures, social softwares, open standards and technologies. Cholion and Karissidappa^[26] described the concepts of academic library consortia in the e-publishing era and highlighted its importance in the current period.

4 Education for Differently-abled Students in Kerala

In India, Kerala stands at the 12th position in terms of population, with a literacy rate of 93.91% is far advanced than other states. In Kerala, there are a total of 7,61,843 differently-abled persons which include 3,94,706 males and 3,67,137 females. This includes persons with visual, hearing, speech, locomotors and mental disabilities. Among the total differently-abled people in Kerala, 1,15,513 persons are visually challenged and 1,46,712 persons are speech and hearing impaired. Highest number of 1,71,630 differently-abled belongs to the category of orthopedically challenged. Persons who are mentally retarded or having mental illness in the state are 1,32,624 and 96,131 persons are having

other types of impairments^[27]. Census data 2011 revealed that 99233 people are suffering multiple disabilities in Kerala^[28].

There are 12615 schools in Kerala and these include government, aided and unaided schools, recognised by the department of education, Government of Kerala^[29]. Total number of 303 special schools in the state, which includes 44 special schools for blind or deaf, 37 government aided schools and 259 private schools under the department of education^[30]. In addition, NGO's are playing a major role in the state for the empowerment and education of differently-abled. A total of 1,52,974 differently-abled students are studying in regular schools in Kerala under SSA^[31], and 28,010 students are studying in regular schools under Integrated Education of the Disabled at Secondary Stage (IEDSS). Table 1

shows the number of differently-abled students studying in high schools and higher secondary schools in Kerala^[32].

4.1 LRC and Assistive Technologies (AT)

As access to information is a major problem for differently-abled students, they need to access resources in alternative formats. ATs can help them to accomplish tasks independently in work place, classroom etc. Rapid advances in information processing, storage and communication technologies have revolutionised the role of libraries worldwide in disseminating information services to their users^[33]. According to World Health Organisation (WHO), AT is a broad concept, covering virtually anything that might be used to compensate for lack of certain abilities ranging from low-tech devices like crutches or a special grip for a pen, to

Table 1: Number of Differently-abled Students in Schools

Schools	Visually Challenged		Physically Challenged		Mentally Retarded		Speech & Hearing Impaired		Other Disabilities	
	RS	SS	RS	SS	RS	SS	RS	SS	RS	SS
IEDSS	4095	454	36010	0	17511	16220 (no age bar)	2467	1887	MI-19 Autism-12 CP-296	-
SSA	71946	--	7949	--	28157	---	15154	--	MI-0 Autism-2333 CP-3230 LD-19658 Multiple disability- 4547	--

(IEDSS-Integrated Education of the disabled at Secondary Stage, SSA-Sarva Siksha Abhiyaan, RS-Regular School, SS- Special Schools)

more advanced items like hearing aids and glasses, to high-tech devices such as braille and computers with specialised software for helping dyslectics to read^[34]. Chakravarty and Mahajan defined it as 'any item, piece of equipment, or product system, whether acquired commercially, modified, or customised, that is used to increase,

maintain, or improve functional capabilities of individuals with disabilities'^[35].

LRCs exist within educational institutions with an objective to build library facilities to support educational, social cultural activities and to promote learning, teaching and research activities by providing resources, indigenous

databases, learning course instructional materials in a networked environment using ICT^[36]. An inclusive library provides information services resources required to meet the information needs of differently-abled students with the help of adequate assistive devices irrespective of their limitations and impairments^[37]. LRC shows the appropriate infrastructural facilities needed to provide information services with assistive technology or device.

5 State Consortium for Inclusive Libraries with Assistive Technologies (SCILAT)

The preliminary observations and the reviews of previous studies show that no efforts have been taken for library cooperation among any type of libraries in the state. In spite of the various advantages of linking libraries together, any appropriate agency has not come forward for organising libraries into networks. In this context a proposal is put forward for bringing all school libraries attached to the education department of the Government of Kerala, and other institutions of national importance. The network can be called State Consortium for Inclusive Libraries with Assistive Technologies (SCILAT). The network will operate in three tier system. A network of the school libraries in the state (high schools and higher secondary schools) is to form one tier. A state level network of the three identified institution networks, controlled by a consortia reconstituted for the purpose, is envisaged as the second tier. The third level consists of the three institutions of national importance under the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Government of India^[38].

The first level will comprise of selected school libraries in the state. This networks will be of varying complexity depending upon the number of schools selected (both government and aided) in the 14 districts and number of schools coming under each category of disability.

There are 12615 inclusive schools and 303 special schools in the state. This level of SCILAT will consist of individual library network for each of the category of disability. For each category, firstly the school libraries which can form part of the network will be identified. The selected libraries must have been automated with internet connectivity, standard software and assistive technologies. All the libraries of schools are to be brought into the consortium with the concerned state institute with the specific disability at the apex. Each network can be converted as a LRC at the state level.

The second tier is formed as a state level network of the institutions as LRCs identified for the three types of disabilities, i.e., physical, visual, hearing impaired, controlled by a network control centre constituted for the purpose. The three institutions identified as the nodal centres in the state are the Centre for Disability Studies (CeDS), Kerala Federation of the Blind (KFB) and National Institute of Speech and Hearing (NISH). CeDS aims to establish resource and information centres relating to disability studies and to foster and provide necessary academic support for social inclusion activities pertaining to the differently-abled students^[39]. KFB is the major agency which provides braille books and talking books all over Kerala^[40]. NISH is a comprehensive, multipurpose institution on national importance dedicated to the total rehabilitation of persons with speech and hearing impairment^[41].

The third tier consists of three specific national institutes identified for the physically challenged, visually challenged and for hearing impaired. They are the National Institute for Locomotor Disabilities, Kolkata (NILD), National Institute for the Empowerment of Persons with Visual Disabilities, Dehradun (NIEPVD) and Ali Yavar Jung National Institute

of Speech and Hearing Disabilities, Mumbai (AYJNISHD) respectively. The NILD (formerly known NIOH, National Institute for the Orthopedically Handicapped) is an apex organisation in the area of loco motor disability that came into the service since 1978 as an autonomous body. The institution is committed in providing services to the orthopedically handicapped population and provides training to physiotherapists, occupational therapists, employment and placement officers and vocational counsellors^[42]. The NIEPVD (formerly known as NIVH, National Institute for the Visually Handicapped) has been working for the welfare of visually impaired persons, is a premier institute in the field of visual disability and it also houses the National Library for the Print Disabled. The institute is largest producer and distributor of Braille literature and devices in the country including talking books^[43]. The AYJNISHD (formerly AYJNIIH, Ali Yavar Jung National Institute for the Hearing Handicapped) is an autonomous organisation deals with various aspects of rehabilitation of the hearing impaired and offers various undergraduate and postgraduate courses^[44].

The school level networks can be linked at the state level institutions, and that will form the SCILAT. A union catalogue of books including braille can be created at the level of each category of schools and can be merged to form the online union catalogue of the consortia. When all the networks are completed with automation and creation of online public access catalogue (OPAC), an online union catalogue of each first level network can be created by the concerned category of schools. All the school libraries and the participating institutes can access books with the help of the SCILAT online union catalogue. A schematic diagram illustrating the functioning of the consortium is shown in the figure 2.

Figure 2: SCILAT structure and layout

The network when developed will consist of the school libraries of 14 districts in Kerala and other regional and national institutes. They can share the resources of all libraries and LRCs in the network and become part of the consortia. In order to streamline, control, and evaluate the functions of the SCILAT, there will be a governing body consisting of representatives of school principals and librarians, from each institutes included and the network. The library expert and the software expert will be the ex-officio members of the council. One of the institutes in the state will be identified as the control centre. The Consortia Control Centre (CCC) will have autonomous status and it will be directly under the Government of Kerala.

The major responsibilities of the CCC envisaged the following:

- It should provide adequate resources and necessary infrastructure including the proper assistive devices, its implementation,

maintenance and overall supervision, and to develop disabled friendly library management software suited to the school libraries of the state.

- It should provide the resources to the school libraries, training in using assistive technologies, training the library staff, curriculum developing, translation of books into audio, Braille formats and academic books.
- It should aim in developing ATs and software's which helps to provide adequate assistive devices at cheaper rate to the libraries.

There are several challenges faced in managing the proposed consortia^[45].

- Establishment and maintenance of network,
- Identification and maintenance of knowledge and expertise,
- Funding management,
- Coordinating among the stakeholders, departments and the ministries,
- Implementation and monitoring of the system in the local, regional and national level.

5.1 Objectives

The main objective of the SCILAT and the consortia control centre is that, it will help the LRC to act as a centre for information processing, knowledge management and skill development. It helps the LRCs to act as a depository and to control the functioning of school libraries in the state. The objectives include:

- to ensure continuous subscription of the books and learning materials,
- to encourage collection development in the LRCs,
- to procure ATs and to use them properly,
- to share technical expertise of library professionals,

- to provide a platform for discussing and sharing professional issues and concerns,
- to reduce the unit cost of information purchased.

5.2 Policy Endorsement

It is crucial for the success of the consortia that there must be an endorsement of the policy at the government and management level since many of the libraries are part of the state government. Hence it is mandatory to have a formal endorsement from the government for the formation of the proposed consortium. In order to share the resources of the school libraries, it is necessary for all the participating libraries to sign a memorandum of understanding (MoU) which clearly states the common objectives, constitution of consortium, modus operandi etc.

5.3 Structure

The proposed consortium must be centrally organised. There must be a governing body comprising selected principals, librarians or information officers of participating school libraries and institutes. One of them shall act as a chief coordinator on rotation basis. The consortium control centre will act as the major hub of the network. Separate bodies shall be formed for negotiation, technical aspects, publications, training etc. The participating schools and institutes can develop local resources and assistive technologies for the students with special needs.

6 Suggestions

The following suggestions are given based on the proposal.

- Schools providing inclusive education in the state should take initiative in catering the information needs of the differently-abled students by providing with ATs and special fund for the provision of procuring it.

- The state government and the school management should employ or fund the training of librarians and teachers.
- Inclusive education schools should seek ways to partner with local bodies, NGOs and other donor agencies to improve their technology infrastructure and facilitate improvements to service delivery.
- With the help of LRC, library organisations can develop orientation programmes to librarians and teachers on serving patrons with disabilities.
- Agencies of the state government concerned with policy formulation and monitoring such as the SCERT, SSA, general education department as well as Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment should seek collaboration with authors, publishers and printers of recommended books in schools, with a view to producing alternative versions in Braille and speech-media. This will improve local availability of information sources and Atrs and possibly enable the schools to acquire them.

7 Conclusion

Libraries play a key role in building an inclusive society and to achieve this, it must be inclusive and barrier free. The school libraries in Kerala need to be strengthened both as virtual and physical entities. The potential of new technological developments and assistive technologies should be fully harnessed to enhance and promote the services for the users. The consortia of LRCs with assistive technologies will be beneficial for those institutes which are responsible for organising developmental, remedial and recreational programme for the students with special needs. The proposed consortia is expected to encourage

teachers, librarians and information professionals serving the differently-abled students in the state to improve the quality of services and assistive devices, thereby facilitating positive attitude towards students. Hence the establishment of SCILAT would definitely lead to a quantum leap in the library services and assistive technologies of differently-abled students in the state. Unrestricted access to a wide range of information resources in LRCs would enable the students with various disabilities to enrich their knowledge base and get equal opportunities for education and training. It will empower them to take active part in the general cultural, and other societal roles. Consequently, the establishment of a exclusive and fully equipped consortia would be an important step in attaining inclusive education and integration into the society as a whole. The steps for the design of a resource sharing network surely will help the stake holders as well as the policy makers in the state to implement the suggestions and proposals. The proposed consortium will help the information to reach the unreached. With the help of internet and adaptive technologies equal access to information can be provided to all sections of the society.

References

1. ROY (P C) and BANDYOPADHYAY (R). Designing barrier free services for visually challenged persons in the academic libraries in India. 2009. http://crl.du.ac.in/ical09/papers/index_files/ical-105_241_602_1_RV.pdf (Retrieved on: Mar 12, 2020).
2. INDIA. Ministry of Law, Justice and Company Affairs. *The persons with disabilities (equal opportunities, protection of rights, and full participation) act, 1995*. Govt. of India; New Delhi.
3. SANJEEV (K) and KUMAR (K). Inclusive education in India. *Electronic Journal of*

- Inclusive Education*. 2, 2; 2007. Article 7. <https://corescholar.libraries.wright.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1086&context=ejie> (Retrieved on: May 03, 2020).
4. BINDAL(S) and SHARMA (S). Inclusive education in Indian context. *Journal of Indian Education*. 35, 4; 2010. p 34-45.
 5. INDIA. Ministry of Human Resources Development. *Action Plan for inclusive education of children and youth with disabilities*. 2005. Government of India; New Delhi. <http://www.education.nic.in>. (Retrieved on: Mar 12, 2020).
 6. INDIA. Ministry of Human Resources Development. *District Primary Education Programme (DPEP)*. 1997. Govt. of India, New Delhi,
 7. REHABILITATION COUNCIL of India. <http://rehabcouncil.nic.in/> (Retrieved on: Mar 12, 2020).
 8. CHAKRABORTI (S) and GHOSH (S B). Inclusive education in India: a developmental milestone from segregation to inclusion. *Journal of Education System*. 1,1; 2017. p 53-62.
 9. INDIA. Ministry of Human Resources Development. *National Education Policy*. 2020. Govt. of India; New Delhi. https://www.mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf (Retrieved on: April 18, 2020).
 10. NISBET (Paul). Assistive technologies to access print resources for students with visual impairment: implications for accommodations in high stakes assessments. *British Journal of Visual Impairment*. 38,2; 2020. p 222-47. doi: 10.1177/0264619619899678
 11. ROY (Protap Chandra), BANDYOPADHYAY (Ratna) and PANIGRAHI (Pijushkanti). Role of libraries in facilitating students with visual impairment in the Institutes of Higher Education of West Bengal : an analytical study. *IASLIC Bulletin*. 64, 1; 2019. p.40-58.
 12. RAVINDRAN (K). A plan proposal for modernisation and networking of Academic Libraries in Kerala to Achieve Consolidation and Optimum Utilisation of Resources. *ILIS Journal of Librarianship and Informatics*. 2, 2; 2019. p 7-14.
 13. KHOWAJA (Sufia) and FATIMA (Nishat). Knowledge resources for visually impaired persons: an indian perspective. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. 2019, Paper 3059. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/3059> (Retrieved on: Jun 15, 2020).
 14. MAHAWARIYA (K). A study of needs and requirements of visually impaired students of University of Delhi. *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*. 9, 2; 2019. p 83-4.
 15. ROY (Protap Chandra), BANDYOPADHYAY (Ratna) and PANIGRAHI (Pijushkanti). Challenges faced by visually impaired students in higher education : a case study based on the University of Calcutta. *RBU Journal of Library and Information Science*. 20; 2018. p 3-14.
 16. BHARDWAJ (R K). Information access mechanism for visually impaired students in higher educational institutions: a study. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*. 38,6; 2018. p 387-95, doi: 10.14429/djlit.38.6.13603.
 17. NANDI (Ratna), PANIGRAHI (Pijushkanti) and RATH (Durgasankar). Changing paradigm of consortia: a retrospective analysis. *IASLIC Bulletin*. 62, 2; 2017. p 114-26
 18. DESAI (S), MANTHA (S) and PHALLE (V M). Assistive technology solution for disabled population of India. In International Conference on Current Trends in Computer, Electrical, Electronics and Communication; Mysore. 2017. p311-5, doi: 10.1109/CTCEEC.2017.8455072.
 19. GUPTA (S). Accessibility beyond disability and welfare. *Yojana*. 60, 5; 2016. p 18-21.
 20. ABDELRAHMAN (O H). Use of library technology and services by the visually impaired and the blind in the University of Khartoum, Sudan. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*. 36,3; 2016. p 93-7.

38. INDIA. Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment. <http://socialjustice.nic.in/> (Retrieved on: May 12, 2020).
39. CENTRE FOR disability studies. <http://cdskerala.org/cds/> (Retrieved on: May 12, 2020).
40. KERALA FEDERATION of the blind. <https://kfbindia.org/> (Retrieved on: May 12, 2020).
41. NATIONAL INSTITUTE of Speech and Hearing. <http://www.nish.ac.in/> (Retrieved on: May 12, 2020).
42. NATIONAL INSTITUTE for locomotor disabilities (Divyangjan) <http://www.niohkol.nic.in/> (Retrieved on: May 12, 2020).
43. NATIONAL INSTITUTE for the empowerment of Persons with Visual Disabilities. <http://nivh.gov.in/> (Retrieved on: May 12, 2020).
44. ALI YAVAR JUNG National Institute of Speech and Hearing Disabilities. <http://www.ayjnihh.nic.in/> (Retrieved on: May 12, 2020).
45. BISWAS (Bidan Chand) and DASGUPTA (Swapan K). Opportunities for libraries in managing resource sharing through consortia: a new challenge for Indian Libraries. International Caliber-2003. Feb 13- 15,2003. INFLIBNET;

A h m e d a b a d . 2 0 0 3 . p 2 9 1 - 7 .
<http://ir.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/1944/196>
 (Retrieved on: Jun 22, 2020).

Dr V S Midhula Soman is presently working as College Librarian in Sree Sankara College, Kalady, Kerala. She obtained her MLISc and PhD from the University of Kerala, and BSc (Botany) from the University College, Thiruvananthapuram. Her areas of interest include: Digital Reference Service, User Studies, Assistive Technologies and Digital Libraries. She has contributed several research papers in peer reviewed journals, national and international conferences and in books.

Dr K G Sudhier is an Assistant Professor of Library & Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, India. He received his MLISc and PhD degree from the University of Kerala. Previously he worked in the University of Kerala as a Librarian and Assistant Professor. An author of over 55 papers in peer reviewed accredited journals and over 80 conference papers in proceedings, chapters in books and popular articles. His recent research on the Mapping of Bioinformatics research was supported by the Dept. of Science & Technology, Govt. of India. He specialises in science communication, scholarly publishing and scientometrics. Sudhier is on the editorial board of few journals and reviewer for several journals.

